

ASSESSMENT OF THE CURRENT CONDITIONS OF TECHNICAL COLLEGE BUILDINGS IN BAUCHI STATE FOR IMPROVING SAFETY

Dazar Luka¹, P. S. Yaduma², Bulus Tausayi³, Luka Ishaya Daniel⁴ and Yakubu Sarki Adangs⁵

Department of Vocational and Technology Education, Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University, Bauchi, Bauchi State.

Email: dazarluka@gmail.com

Abstract

This study assessed the current conditions of Technical College Buildings in Bauchi State, Nigeria under classroom buildings, hostel buildings, workshop buildings laboratory buildings and examination hall buildings. The study was guided by one research question and corresponding hypothesis. Relevant literatures related to the research question were reviewed. The study adopted survey research design and total sample population was used for this study. Thirty-one respondents were used in the study comprising of Twenty-seven (27) administrators from the eight (8) Technical Colleges of Bauchi State (Principal and Vice Principals), Director/Deputy Directors science and technology of the Bauchi State Ministry of Education and four maintenance officers respectively. The instrument used for the study was a structured questionnaire and was validated by three experts. The reliability coefficient of the instrument was found to be .875 and hence the instrument was found to be reliable. Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 21 was used to analyse the data that was collected. The data obtained was analysed using Descriptive Statistics of Mean and Standard Deviation. Through the data collected for this study, it was discovered that all the buildings of the Bauchi State Technical Colleges are in a bad and deplorable working condition and therefore need a maintenance. Based on the findings of this research, the researcher wishes to recommend that All Technical College buildings in Bauchi State should be renovated as this will this enable the students learn comfortably without the fear of the building collapsing on them.

Keywords: Assessment, Technical College, Buildings, Improving Safety

Introduction

There is a general belief that the conditions of facilities in schools and the environment have an important impact on education development. Educational facilities are needed to facilitate effective education development and learning. It is also noteworthy that decent school buildings enhance teaching and learning thereby making the process meaningful and purposeful. Thus, School buildings are crucial because they foster effective pedagogy and boost good result (Iyamu, Imasuen, & Osakue, 2018). The quality and standard of a school is ideally rooted on the provision of sufficiency, operation and supervision of educational facilities. Looking at the deplorable state of public buildings across the country for decades, a large chunk of the country's resources has been channelled towards Transportation Infrastructure, Government administrative Buildings for ministries and Parastatals, Colleges of

Education, Universities, Primary and Secondary Schools (Eke, Musa, Fashubaa, & Abass, 2017). In spite of millions of Naira spent to erect all these buildings, they are left, as soon as commissioned to face premature but steady and rapid deterioration, decay and dilapidation (Adenuga, 2012).

While existing infrastructures in some public schools are in deplorable condition, others are below acceptable standards and, in few cases, non-existent. In the same hostels buildings revealed the dire state of neglect of the school, which is a reflection of most public schools in the country. Worried by the deplorable infrastructural facilities across public schools, a non-governmental organisation, Socio-Economic Rights and Accountability Project (SERAP) has asked President Muhammadu Buhari to probe billions allegedly missing from Universal Basic Education Commission (UBEC) and State Universal Basic Education Board (SUBEB), including N3.2bn for Safe School Initiative.

Accordingly, a report by National Center for Education Statistics and the National Cooperative Education Statistics System (2003). Planning Guide For Maintaining School Facilities (n.d.) states that school buildings are one of the important facilities for getting basic knowledge in everyday life. Maintenance of school building is also required to serve staff and students well-being. To this end effective school maintenance protects capital investment, ensures the health and safety of the students, and supports educational performance. The condition of buildings in public secondary schools in Nigeria has been variously established in Literature. Results from these studies indicate that most of the buildings in the schools were in poor conditions. The Federal Minister of Education, following a nation-wide tour of the schools in 1997, reported that the physical condition of most schools was pathetic which has negatively affected the education system at all levels (Teboho, 2000).

Some of the reasons for the deplorable situation in the schools are that the education sector, particularly its infrastructure, suffers lack of adequate maintenance attention. Other factors responsible for the current state of the buildings in the public secondary schools were users' attitude, maintenance culture and lack of fund (Izobo-Martins, Dare-Abel, & Ayo-Vaughan, 2014).

Poor building conditions in public secondary schools have been caused by a number of factors. Some of those documented in literature are: Lack of maintenance manual, unskilled professionals in maintenance operations, neglect, poor funding, Pressure from usage, poor maintenance culture and building age.

To this end Kunya (2012) reported that, the defects in building facilities such as defacing of wall surface, rising dampness in structure, floor slab failure and doors and windows defects; leaking roof, foundation failure and sagging at beam has not only increased students' phobia in class, but have also enhanced difficulties in school administration. It is noteworthy that decent school buildings enhance teaching and learning thereby making the process meaningful and purposeful. Therefore, School buildings are crucial because they foster effective pedagogy and boost good result (Iyamu *et al* 2018).

Statement of the Problem

Erecting buildings without a functional maintenance plan or policy for it signal a great danger for the occupant and can lead to serious economic loss. Building school structures with standard materials alongside conscious effort of maintenance make schooling interesting and motivating (Ojara, 2013). However, all technical college buildings are in shambles and deplorable condition. Adenuga and Iyagba (2005) noted that public buildings

in Nigeria are in very poor and deplorable conditions of structural and decorative disrepairs. As a result, it has become increasingly difficult to identify a precisely the existing maintenance strategy and options providing solutions in addressing maintenance problems. In addition, there is a paucity of empirical data on the public secondary school buildings and infrastructure. Maintenance program in Nigeria for instance, according to Ahmed (2000) and Odediran Oladele & Eghenure (2012) has not received much attention in the past as the emphasis is on the development of new properties. Furthermore, there is apparent lack of maintenance practice in Nigeria, and that emphasis is placed on the construction of new buildings and neglecting the aspect of maintenance which commences immediately the builder leaves the site. This is also endorsed by Olagunju (2012) who opined that there is lack of maintenance set up in Nigeria that can sustain the current inadequate housing provision in the country.

However, much is not known and documented on the state-of-the-art assessment of the current conditions of Technical College Buildings in Bauchi State both in the past and present. In view of the problem statement, it has become necessary to engage on a study that will address state of the art assessment of the current conditions of Technical College Buildings in Bauchi State. Hence, the main aim of this study is to find out the current condition of Technical College Buildings in Bauchi State and answered the corresponding research question and hypothesis:

1. What is the current condition of Technical College Buildings in Bauchi State?
2. There is no significance difference between the mean responses of Administrators and Maintenance Officers on the current condition of Technical College Buildings in Bauchi State.

Methodology

The study used a survey research design. The area of the study was Bauchi State. The target population of the study is made of 31 respondents which comprised all the three school administrators (Principal and Vice Principals) from the eight technical Colleges in Bauchi State, four Engineers (Maintenance Officers), one Directors and two deputy directors Science and Technology of the Bauchi State Ministry of Education. Since the population is manageable, the researcher used total sample population. The instrument for data collection in this study was a structured questionnaire developed by the researcher based on the extensive review of the literature related to the study. The questionnaire was sub divided into two sections A and B. Section A consist of categories of the respondents. Section B was a questionnaire which was based on the research questions. Modified Five Point Likert type rating Scale of Excellent (E) -5 Points, Good (G) -4 Points, Acceptable (A) -3 Points, Poor (P) -2 Points and Critical (C) -1 Point was used. Statistical Package for Social Sciences (IBM SPSS) version 21 was used to analyze the data that was collected. The decision rule for the hypotheses depends on the calculated P value, when the P value is greater than 0.05 level of significance.

Results and Discussion

Research Question One: What is the current condition of Technical College Buildings in Bauchi State?

Table 1: Mean and standard deviation of the respondents on the current condition of Technical College Buildings in Bauchi State

$N_A = 27$

$N_M = 4$

S/N	Item Statement	N_A	\bar{X}_A	SD_A	N_M	\bar{X}_M	SD_M	\bar{X}_g	Remark
CLASSROOM BUILDINGS									
Structures									
1.	Construction Drawings	27	2.07	1.035	4	2.50	.577	2.13	Poor
2.	Standard Foundation	27	2.30	.669	4	2.50	.577	2.33	Poor
3.	Slab	27	2.04	.980	4	2.00	0.000	2.03	Poor
4.	Floor Framing	27	1.70	.465	4	1.50	.577	1.67	Critical
5.	Walls	27	2.26	.656	4	2.00	0.000	2.23	Poor
6.	Plaster	27	2.11	.892	4	2.00	0.000	2.10	Poor
7.	Paint	27	2.15	.718	4	2.00	0.000	2.13	Poor
8.	Ceiling	27	2.22	.974	4	1.75	.500	2.16	Poor
9.	Roofs	27	1.96	.898	4	2.00	0.000	1.97	Critical
10.	Mechanical								
	Septic Tanks	27	2.07	.829	4	2.00	0.000	2.06	Poor
	Pipe	27	2.07	.781	4	3.25	1.500	2.22	Poor
	Tap	27	2.37	1.043	4	1.75	.500	2.29	Poor
	Wash basin	27	2.22	.641	4	3.00	.816	2.32	Poor
	Showers	27	2.15	.864	4	2.00	0.000	2.13	Poor
	Bath tube	27	2.15	.949	4	2.00	0.000	2.13	Poor
	Septic tank	27	2.15	.662	4	2.00	0.000	2.13	Poor
11.	Electrical								
	Conduit	27	2.11	.847	4	2.00	0.000	2.10	Poor
	Lightings	27	1.81	.622	4	1.75	.957	1.80	Critical
	Switches	27	1.96	.518	4	2.25	.500	2.00	Poor
	Ceiling Fans	27	2.22	.698	4	2.00	0.000	2.19	Poor
	Sockets	27	2.00	.679	4	2.00	0.000	2.00	Poor
12.	Doors	27	2.00	.784	4	1.50	.577	1.94	Critical
13.	Windows	27	2.19	.834	4	2.00	0.000	2.17	Poor
	Cluster Mean		2.04			2.08		1.92	
HOSTEL BUILDINGS									
Structures									
14.	Construction Drawing	27	2.04	.940	4	1.50	.577	1.97	Critical
15.	Standard Foundation	27	2.26	.903	4	2.00	0.000	2.23	Poor
16.	Slab	27	2.19	.786	4	2.00	0.000	2.17	Poor
17.	Floor Framing	27	2.30	.609	4	2.75	.500	2.36	Poor
18.	Walls	27	2.11	1.086	4	1.25	.500	2.00	Poor
19.	Plaster	27	1.93	.550	4	1.75	.500	1.91	Critical
20.	Paint	27	2.11	.892	4	1.25	.500	2.00	Poor
21.	Roofs	27	2.15	.818	4	2.25	.500	2.16	Poor
22.	Ceiling	27	2.07	.730	4	2.00	0.000	2.06	Poor
23.	Mechanical								
	Septic Tanks	27	2.07	.730	4	1.25	.500	1.96	Critical
	Pipes	27	2.15	1.064	4	2.25	.500	2.16	Poor
	Taps	27	2.00	.480	4	2.00	0.000	2.00	Poor
	Water closet	27	2.15	.770	4	2.00	0.000	2.13	Poor
	Bath tube	27	2.00	.734	4	2.00	0.000	2.00	Poor

	Wash hand basins	27	2.11	.577	4	2.25	.500	2.13	Poor	
	Showers	27	2.04	.518	4	1.75	.500	2.00	Poor	
24.	Electrical									
	Conduit	27	1.96	.759	4	1.50	1.000	1.90	Critical	
	Lightings	27	2.07	.550	4	1.75	.500	2.03	Poor	
	Switches	27	2.22	.751	4	2.25	.500	2.22	Poor	
	Ceiling fans	27	1.93	.474	4	2.25	.500	1.97	Critical	
	Sockets	27	1.96	.649	4	1.25	.500	1.87	Poor	
25.	Doors	27	2.07	.781	4	2.00	0.000	2.06	Poor	
26.	Windows	27	1.89	.506	4	2.25	.500	1.94	Critical	
	Cluster Mean		2.08			1.89		2.05		
WORKSHOP BUILDINGS										
Structures										
27.	Construction Drawings	27	2.19	.736	4	2.00	0.000	2.17	Poor	
28.	Standard Foundation	27	2.07	.730	4	2.25	.500	2.09	Poor	
29.	Slab	27	2.04	.649	4	1.75	.500	2.00	Poor	
30.	Floor Framing	27	2.07	.781	4	2.00	0.000	2.06	Poor	
31.	Walls	27	2.19	.879	4	1.25	.500	2.07	Poor	
32.	Plaster	27	1.93	.550	4	2.00	0.000	1.94	Critical	
33.	Paint	27	1.93	.474	4	1.50	.577	1.87	Critical	
34.	Ceilings	27	2.00	.734	4	2.00	0.000	2.00	Poor	
35.	Roofs	27	2.26	.984	4	2.25	.500	2.26	Poor	
36.	Mechanical									
	Septic Tanks	27	2.07	.874	4	1.25	.500	1.96	Critical	
	Pipes	27	2.30	.993	4	2.25	.500	2.29	Poor	
	Taps	27	2.19	.834	4	2.25	.500	2.20	Poor	
	Wash hand basins	27	1.96	.518	4	2.50	.577	2.03	Poor	
37.	Electrical									
	Conduit	27	2.15	.602	4	2.00	0.000	2.13	Poor	
	Lightings	27	2.11	.698	4	2.25	.500	2.13	Poor	
	Switches	27	1.93	.474	4	1.25	.500	1.84	Critical	
	Sockets	27	2.22	1.086	4	1.50	.577	2.13	Poor	
38.	Doors	27	2.07	.829	4	2.25	.500	2.09	Poor	
39.	Windows	27	1.96	.518	4	2.50	.577	2.03	Poor	
	Cluster Mean		2.09			1.95		2.07		
LABORATORY BUILDINGS										
Structures										
40.	Construction Drawings	27	2.07	.829	4	1.75	.500	2.03	Poor	
41.	Standard Foundation	27	2.04	.854	4	2.00	0.000	2.03	Poor	
42.	Slab	27	2.11	.577	4	2.75	.957	2.19	Poor	
43.	Floor Framing	27	1.93	.474	4	2.25	.500	1.97	Critical	
44.	Walls	27	2.07	.616	4	2.50	.577	2.13	Poor	
45.	Plaster	27	2.07	.781	4	2.00	0.000	2.06	Poor	
46.	Paint	27	2.04	.587	4	2.50	.577	2.10	Poor	
47.	Roofs	27	2.07	.616	4	2.25	.500	2.09	Poor	
48.	Ceilings	27	2.11	.934	4	1.50	.577	2.03	Poor	
49.	Mechanical									
	Septic Tanks	27	2.26	.594	4	2.00	0.000	2.23	Poor	
	Pipes	27	2.11	.698	4	2.50	.577	2.16	Poor	
	Wash hand basins	27	2.19	.879	4	2.25	.500	2.20	Poor	
	Taps	27	2.04	.759	4	2.00	0.000	2.03	Poor	
50.	Electrical									
	Conduit	27	2.15	.818	4	2.50	.577	2.20	Poor	
	Lightings	27	1.96	.518	4	2.25	.500	2.00	Poor	
	Switches	27	2.00	.480	4	1.50	.577	1.94	Critical	

	Ceiling fans	27	2.15	.949	4	2.00	.816	2.13	Poor	
	Sockets	27	2.15	.864	4	2.00	0.000	2.13	Poor	
51.	Doors	27	2.30	.869	4	2.25	.500	2.29	Poor	
52.	Windows	27	2.07	.616	4	2.75	.500	2.16	Poor	
	Cluster Mean		2.09			2.18		2.11		
EXAMINATION HALL BUILDINGS										
Structures										
53.	Construction Drawings	27	1.89	.577	4	2.00	0.000	1.90	Critical	
54.	Standard Foundation	27	1.89	.506	4	2.25	.500	1.94	Critical	
55.	Slab	27	1.96	.898	4	2.25	.500	2.00	Poor	
56.	Floor Framing	27	1.89	.751	4	2.00	0.000	1.90	Critical	
57.	Walls	27	1.96	.518	4	2.25	.500	2.00	Poor	
58.	Plaster	27	2.26	.813	4	2.00	0.000	2.23	Poor	
59.	Paint	27	2.22	.934	4	2.50	.577	2.26	Poor	
60.	Ceilings	27	2.15	.456	4	2.00	0.000	2.13	Poor	
61.	Roofs	27	2.04	.518	4	2.50	.577	2.03	Poor	
62.	Mechanical									
	Septic Tanks	27	1.96	.437	4	1.25	.500	1.87	Critical	
	Pipes	27	2.15	.818	4	2.00	1.155	2.13	Poor	
	Wash hand basins	27	2.22	.751	4	2.25	.500	2.22	Poor	
63	Electrical									
	Conduit	27	2.63	.712	4	2.50	.577	2.61	Poor	
	Lightings	27	2.04	.649	4	2.50	.577	2.10	Poor	
	Switches	27	2.22	.847	4	2.25	.500	2.22	Poor	
	Ceiling fans	27	2.11	.698	4	2.25	.500	2.13	Poor	
	Socket outlets	27	2.11	.801	4	2.00	0.000	2.10	Poor	
64.	Doors	27	2.11	.698	4	2.50	.577	2.16	Poor	
65	Windows	27	2.19	.786	4	2.25	.500	2.20	Poor	
	Cluster Mean		2.11			2.18		2.11		

Source: Fieldwork, 2022

Table 1 shows the Mean and Standard Deviation of the respondents' responses on the current condition of Technical College Buildings. The Table showed the Classroom Buildings has cluster mean of 2.04 for Administrators and 2.08 for Maintenance Officers, the grand mean of the classroom of the building is 1.92 which indicates that the classroom building is in critical condition. Table 2 further showed the cluster mean of the Hostel Building to be 2.08 and 1.89 for Administrators and Maintenance Officers, the grand mean of the Hostel Building is 2.05 which showed that the building is in a poor condition. Furthermore, Table 1 showed the Mean of the Workshop Building to be 2.09 and 1.95 for both the Administrators and Maintenance Officers, the grand mean of the workshop building is 2.07 which means the building is in a poor condition. In the same manner the table 2 showed the cluster mean of the respondents on Laboratory Building is 2.09 for Administrator and 2.18 for Maintenance Officers, the grand mean is 2.11 which indicates that the Laboratory Building is in a poor condition. Lastly, Table 2 showed Examination Hall Buildings has cluster mean of 2.11 for Administrators and 2.18 for Maintenance Officer, the grand mean of the building is 2.11 which indicates that Laboratory Building is in a poor condition.

Result of Null Hypothesis

Table 2 X for Administrators and Maintenance Officers on research question one

$N_A=27$

$N_M=4$

S/N	Buildings	X_A	SD_A	X_M	SD_M	X_g
1.	Classroom Buildings	2.04	.784	2.08	.308	1.92
2.	Hostel Buildings	2.08	.724	1.89	.373	2.05
3.	Workshop Buildings	2.09	.734	1.95	.385	2.07
4.	Laboratory Buildings	2.09	.715	2.18	.437	2.11
5.	Examination Hall Building	2.11	.693	2.18	.423	2.11
	Cluster Mean	2.09		2.05		2.04

There is no significance difference between the mean responses of Administrators and Maintenance Officers on the current condition of Technical College Buildings in Bauchi State.

The result of the independent t-test is presented in Table 7 below which showed that there is no significance difference between the mean response of Administrators and Maintenance Officers on the current condition of Technical College Buildings in Bauchi State within the df of 23, t-value = 0.052, p = .959. Since the p value is greater than the confidence level ($P>0.05$) therefore, the null hypothesis was accepted. This implied that there was no significance difference in the mean responses of Administrators and Maintenance Officers on the current condition of Technical College Buildings in Bauchi State.

Table 3 t-test analysis of the mean responses of Administrators and Maintenance Officers on the current condition of Technical College Buildings in Bauchi State.

	N	X	S.D	Df	t	P	Decision
Administrators	27	2.09	.761				
				23	0.052	.959	Accepted
Maintenance Officers	4	2.05	.382				

Finding

The finding of this study indicated that all the buildings of Bauchi State Technical Colleges are in deplorable condition and therefore need a maintenance. Hence the result of the hypothesis was upheld. Therefore,

there is no significant difference between the mean response of Administrators and maintenance Officers on the current condition of Technical College Building of Bauchi State.

Discussion of Findings

Findings of this study shows that all the buildings of Bauchi State Technical Colleges are in deplorable condition and therefore need a maintenance. Generally, the findings further shows that Technical College Building in Bauchi State are not in a good condition. This finding is line with that of Eke et al 2017 who reported that many public schools building and government-owned facilities are not well maintained and in poor condition. Furthermore, the finding agrees with that of Babayo, 2017 who also reported that in Bauchi State especially in the suburb areas, most of the school buildings are in shambles. Some of them still wear the look of the 80s and the work of Adenuga and Iyagba (2005) which noted that public buildings in Nigeria are in very poor and deplorable conditions of structural and decorative disrepairs is in line with the findings of this research. The study also revealed that the existing building stocks in the schools were in a state of decay due to lack of maintenance and repair. Lastly this finding is also in concord with the work Izobo-Martins, et al (2014) who similarly confirmed that most public secondary school buildings in Ogun State Nigeria are in very poor and deplorable conditions of infrastructural disrepair and Asiyai (2012) who also reported that the condition of school facilities in the public secondary schools in Delta State, Nigeria were generally in a state of disrepair and the maintenance operations carried out on the school facilities were inadequate for majority of the facilities which led to excess pressure on available facilities respectively.

Conclusion

From the findings of this study, it shows that Technical College Buildings are in shamble and in a very pathetic situation and hence the need for the Technical Colleges to adopt a maintenance practice which will help in the maintenance of the College buildings.

Recommendations

All Technical College buildings in Bauchi State should be renovated as this will this enable the students learn comfortably without the fear of the building collapsing on them.

References

- Adejimi, A. (2015). Poor Building Maintenance are Architects Free from Blames? *A Paper Presented at the ENHR International Conference on Housing: New Challenges and Innovations in Tomorrow's Cities Iceland*.
- Adenuga, O. A. and Iyagba, R. O. A. (2005). Strategic Approach to Maintenance Practices for Public Buildings in Lagos State. *Lagos Journal of Environmental Studies*, 5(1), 20-28
- Adenuga, O. A. (2012). Maintenance management practices in public hospital built environment: Nigeria case study. *Journal of Sustainable Development in Africa* 14(1), 185-201.
- Ahmed, A. (2000). Management System in Maintenance of Infrastructure. *Fahimta Publishing Company, Kaduna, Nigeria*.
- Asiyai R. I. (2012). Assessing School Facilities in Public Secondary Schools of Delta State. *An International Multidisciplinary Journal, Ethiopia*, 192-205.

- Babayemi, A. (2006). *Principalship. I*, J.B. Babalola, A.O. Ayeni, S.O. Adedeji, A.A. Suleman and M.O. Arike Wuyo (Eds) Educational Management; Thoughts and Practice. Ibadan; Codat Publications.
- Babayo Y. A (2017). Assessment of Schools Facilities and Utilization Time-Rate at Technical College Level within Bauchi States. *International Journal of Education and Evaluation ISSN 2489-0073 Vol. 3 No. 5 2017* www.iardpub.org
- Eke Emmanuel Chidi, Musa Shamsudeen, Fashubaa Taiwo Oladipupo and Abass Jimoh Owolabi (2017): An Assessment of Maintenance Culture on Public Buildings in Nigeria (A Case Study of Osun State). *IOSR Journal of Mechanical and Civil Engineering (IOSR-JMCE) e-ISSN: 2278-1684,p-ISSN: 2320-334X, Volume 14, Issue 5 Ver. III (Sep. - Oct. 2017), PP 53-57* www.iosrjournals.org
- Iyamu Ikponmwen Florence, Imasuen Kennedy and Osakue Elometse Felicia (2018): Analysis of Maintenance Culture in Public Primary and Secondary Schools in Edo State. *International Journal of Vocational and Technical Education Research Vol.4, No.2, pp.23-30, May 2018.*
- Izobo-Martins, O. O., Dare-Abel, O. A., & Ayo-Vaughan, K. (2014). Infrastructure Conditions In Public Secondary Schools, Ogun State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Civil, Structural ,Environmental and Infrastructure Engineering Research and Development, 18-23.*
- Kunya, S.U. (2012). *Maintenance Management* Unpublished M Tech Construction Management Lecture Notes, Building programme, faculty of Environmental Technology, Abubakar, Tafawa Balewa University of Technology, Bauchi, Nigeria.
- Nyapson, Chuhwak Gyang (2015). *Skill Improvement Needs of Self-Employed Technical College Motor Vehicle Mechanic Graduates in Plateau State.* Masters Thesis
- Obidoa, M. (2006). Enhancing The Instructional Supervisory Skills of Principals of Secondary Schools. Principals Year Book. *A Publication of all Nigerian Conference of Principals of Secondary Schools (ANCOPSS). Nsukka, Nigeria: Moke Social Publishers*
- Odediran, S. J.,Oladele, A. O. & Eghenure, F. O. (2012). Maintenance of Residential Buildings: Users' Practices in Nigeria; *Journal of Emerging Trends in Economics and Management Sciences (JETEMS) 3(3): 261-265*
- Ojara, E.S. (2013): The Challenges of Housing Maintenance in Nigeria. Unpublished HND Project, Department of Building Technology, The Federal Polytechnic Ado Ekiti.
- Olagunju, R.E. (2012). Predictive Modelling for Sustainable Residential Building Maintenance in Developing Countries: A Nigerian Case. *Interdisciplinary Journal of Contemporary Research in Business. 4(6):1237-1283.*
- Shardy Abdullah, Arman Abdul Razak, Mohd Hanizun Hanafi & Mohd Najib Salleh. (2015). Managing Government Property Assets: The Main Issues From the Malaysian Perspective. *Journal of Techno-Social, 3(1), 35-52.*
- Uyanga, R. E. (2008). The principal and Education Reform Agenda of the Nigerian Economic Empowerment Development Strategy (NEEDS) and the Millennium Developmental Goals (Mdgs). *A Publication of The Mandatory Continuing Professional Training (MCPT) Programme of the all Nigerian Conference of Principals Of Secondary Schools (ANCOPSS) (Pp. 94-102).*